

HOLISM AND REDUCTIONISM IN SOCIOLOGICAL THEORIES

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Kali charan Sabat

Assistant Professor

NMIMS Global Access School for Continuing Education
V. L. Mehta Road, Vile Parle (W), Mumbai

Abstract

The concepts of holism and reductionism are always debated in the sociological discussions and at times have played very important role in the progress of sociological theory. But unfortunately scientists as of now have not used them in an unambiguous and in absolute coherent way. Instead they have used it to cover a mass of somewhat interrelated but partially different phenomena within sociological theory (Willy Ostreng, n.d.). This article is an effort to reduce this conceptual confusion by exploring and illuminating some of the different ways in which the terms holism and reductionism are used in selected sociological theories. In sociological theories holism is studied in whole and not in parts whereas reductionism emphasizes on the classical Newtonian assumption that says the dynamics of any intricate system can be understood from studying the properties of its parts. Holism has plenty of application in the areas of marketing, medicine and healthcare, agricultural research, and Architecture. Reductionism has plenty of applications in the areas of applied science, physic chemistry and molecular biology.

Key words: Holism, Reductionism, Sociological, Feasibility, Ontological, Philosophical.

1. Introduction

The terms holism and reductionism are used in different notion in different areas of scientific experiments. This paper is an effort to simplify some aspects of the debate between holism and reductionism in sociological theory. There are scientists who argue that the holistic approach will ultimately result in a grand theory for any theory building approach, but at the same time there are those putting up persuasive arguments alongside, stressing the feasibility of mid-range integrative theories (Jens Allwood, n.d.)

The mutual comprehensiveness between holism and reductionism is not to deny that the two processes have differences in their agenda and that the penalizing pulls could act as serious barrier in nurturing inter-disciplinarily in theory building process. Amid the many barriers needed to be overcome are the multiplicities of sub-disciplinary factors that sometimes may seem impassable to experts coming from outside into the process (Michael Ruse, 2005). This sometimes may lead into confusions, frustration and incomprehension among the team members during the beginning of projects. The enticement is to revert

back to the comfort zone of one's own familial territory and leave overseas territories to those who are motivated to work in complex environment.

2. Holism

The term "holism" was first introduced by Jan Smuts in 1926, a South African statesman, in his book "Holism and Evolution". Smuts' (1926) definition for holism was "tendency in nature to form wholes that are greater than the sum of the parts through creative evolution". Thus, holism is studied in whole and not in parts. Possibly the most fundamental argument in the sociological holism is "a whole is something that is more than the sum of its parts or a whole that has properties which are independent of and are different from the properties of its parts" (Natke H G & Cempel C, n.d.).

The holists' approach, hold that incredible new and exciting happens when folks combine and start to interact with each other. These results into concept called "social wholes", these social wholes are just as existent as the individuals that make up the social wholes. But most notably, they have properties that are very different and distinct from the properties of the individuals that constitute the social whole (Smuts, 1926). Thus, the properties of a social whole are not reducible to the properties of its constituent parts. The above discussion may be explained by means of an example given in the first chapter of Adam Smith's "The wealth of nations". In the chapter Smith (1963) explains on the division of labor concept by means of the example of a pin factory. Smith points out that a pin-maker working on his own could at most produce 20 pins a day, but if he got together with some other pin-makers and started manufacturing together, the result would be much better. That's how we can support the holists' argument that something new and exciting happens when individuals join together and start to interact with each other.

3. Applications of Holism

Agriculture: In agricultural science techniques such as perma-culture and holistic planned grazing (integration of ecology and social sciences with food production) are extensively used. Agricultural scientists many times consider organic farming to be as holistic approach.

Medicine: In health care the term "holistic," has been used to describe approaches that take into account factors such as biological, psychological, social issues and other intuitive judgments while treating the patients.

Marketing: The holistic branding approach tries to project a uniform brand image globally. For example Hard rock café maintains a universal brand image across all countries, including the whole lot from advertising styles to the ambiance and products they offer.

Architecture: In Architecture holism tends to involve an all-inclusive design perspective in different projects.

4. Reductionism

In reductionism concept, the emphasis is on the classical Newtonian assumption that says the dynamics of any intricate system can be understood from studying the properties of its parts. Complex systems are

therefore divided down into their components and sub-components, and each part is studied independently by mode of disciplinary and sub-disciplinary approaches. The problem is to find the entry points from where we can tackle the issues of the system. But, once one understands the parts, the dynamics of the whole can be derived very systematically. In recent times, social scientists have been so successful in applying this technique that instead of reverting back to see how their findings fit in with the totality, they have persistent enough to dig deeper into their specialties, continuously narrowing the focus of their research.

The Oxford Companion to Philosophy discusses three types of reductionism:

Ontological reductionism: It says that the whole of truth consists of a least number of parts. It is a form of monism, which claims that all programs, processes, projects, and events are reducible to a single core. Ontological reductionism is the claim that everything that exists is made from a small number of basic substances that behave in regular ways.

Methodological reductionism: It is a scientific try to provide justification in terms of very smaller fragmented entities. In methodological reductionism the processes and events are explained by breaking them into smaller entities.

Theory reductionism: It states that a newer theory does not substitute or absorb the old theory, but instead reduces it to more basic ones. Theory reduction can be divided into three types: 1) Translation, 2) Derivation and 3) Explanation. Theoretical reduction thus is the diminution of one theory to another, or we can say it is the inclusion of idea about a particular thing into another idea to get a new simpler idea.

5. Applications of Reductionism

Reductionism in Sociology can be applied to processes, phenomena, projects, explanations, and theories. In applied science, reductionism is considered to be the foundations of chemistry, and base for different theories in physics and molecular biology (Peter Schuster, n. d.; Donato Bergandi & Patrick Blandin, 1998).

6. Conclusion

The most significant finding from the study is that there are no philosophical or practical contradictions between holism and reductionism in scientific creation. But there is slight difference in the process between holism and reductionism approaches, while the holist strictly differentiates relational from non-relational characters; the reductionist includes them all in a systematic single unit.

7. References

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